

Dynamics in the Time -Dependent Schrodinger Equation

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In earlier notes, it was argued the quantum mechanical wavefunction is a function which mimics $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ in terms of transformations $x \rightarrow x+a$ and $t \rightarrow t+ b$ (a, b infinitesimal), but with p and E replaced with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$. The conditional average takes account of two channels which are periodically linked. $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } f_p(t) p \exp(ipx)] / W(x,t)$. It seems these ideas carry over into special relativity. In this note, we try to consider why both $\exp(iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ should both be periodic. (We do not use the idea of $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ representing a wave.) Next, we investigate how the transformational properties of $W(x,t)$ lead to $d/dx E(x,t) = -d/dt p(x,t)$ where d/dx and d/dt are partial derivatives. This equation, we argue describes a certain aspect of dynamics present in the time dependent case which is absent in the time independent one. We also examine how these ideas seem to provide information about the uncertainty principle both for p and E . Finally, we examine a linear relativistic theory in the literature (1) and compare it to the case of conditional averaging.

$\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$

In the literature, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is sometimes used to describe a wave, with E and p being linked by an equation (e.g. $E=p^2/2m$ nonrelativistic). In this note, we argue that somehow energy is equivalent to a two channel system ($\cos(Et)$ and $\sin(Et)$) with the two being periodically linked. In other words, energy is described as a frequency. The question is whether this has any implications on momentum. In the nonrelativistic case, $p=mv$ and in the relativistic $p = m_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ ($c=1$). Thus it seems to loosely be a kind of flux, in one case of m_0 and in the other of $m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. " m_0 ", the rest mass, is a type of energy and so should exhibit the two channel periodic linking of $\exp(-iEt)$. Given that m_0 is travelling through space, this seems to be exhibited as $\exp(ipx)$. Even though this argument is "hand-wavy", quantum mechanics seems to show there is a strong link between E (the full energy including rest mass, kinetic and potential energy) and the somewhat "free" motion associated with $\exp(ipx)$. In quantum mechanics p is conditionally averaged with weights which are linked to the full energy and potential etc through the Schrodinger equation or a relativistic equation such as the Klein-Gordon equation or Dirac equation, nevertheless it is used to calculate an average $\langle p^2 \rangle$ which at a given x and t is an average of a free particle.

Dynamics

If one defines energy and momentum fluxes as:

$E(x,t) = i d/dt W(x,t) / W(x,t)$ and $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = -i d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)$ then one may show that:

$d/dx E(x,t) = -d/dt \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ where d/dx and d/dt are partial derivatives. ((1))

This equation as noted follows from the fact that $d/dt W(x,t) = i \langle E \rangle W(x,t)$ and $d/dx W(x,t) = -i \langle p \rangle W(x,t)$. Thus, given that $W(x,t)$ mimics $\exp(iEt - ipx)$ in small transformations in x and t , which is related to dynamics, one has ((1)), a dynamical equation which should hold in both relativistic and nonrelativistic cases. In order to gain insight into ((1)), consider the nonrelativistic Schrodinger case where:

$$\langle p \rangle = \left[\sum \text{over } p \text{ } f_p(t) p \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x,t) \quad \text{and} \quad \langle p^*p \rangle = \left[\sum \text{over } p \text{ } f_p(t) p^*p \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x,t)$$

The latter is related to kinetic energy and appears directly in the Schrodinger equation. The former does not, yet is a physical entity (it seems) of importance. As argued in other notes, it is as if one has two velocities. For the time-independent non-relativistic case, E is a constant in x and t and $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is a function of x . Thus, it seems that $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ undergoes acceleration, but not according to Newton's law (except in the case of the ground state of an oscillator). $\langle p^*p \rangle$ on the other hand changes according to Newton's law because it is part of an energy conservation equation (i.e. the Schrodinger equation):

$$1/2m \langle p^*p \text{ conditional} \rangle + V(x) = E \quad \text{is equivalent to the Schrodinger equation.}$$

Not only does $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ accelerate, but it may exhibit periodic behaviour. It does not change in time, however, for the time-independent case. In the time-dependent case ((1)), both relativistic and nonrelativistic, however, it does change in time. $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ represents a two channel average of p with weights $f_p(t)$ linked to the full energy and potential. Thus, it looks like "free particle motion" at an instant, but is constrained. In classical physics, $.5mv^2$ also looks like a free particle at an instant, but v changes in x and t in a constrained manner. We argue that quantum mechanics and classical mechanics are similar in this respect. They both consider changes to a "free particle", although in quantum mechanics this free particle is a constrained average. Thus, the dynamics of ((1)) seem to show that $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ may change in time at a given x_1 (perhaps due to a $V(x,t)$), and this must be equivalent to the change in the total $E(x,t)$ (including rest mass, kinetic energy and potential energy) in space (i.e. d/dx). This is a consequence of the one function $W(x,t)$ changing in space as $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and in time as $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle = E(x,t)$. Thus, it seems the extra change in $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ in time at x_1 , which represents a different type of acceleration (not $d/dx \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$) upsets the balance of a constant E in x and t and creates a gradient of energy in space. This idea should also hold for the relativistic case. Thus, $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ although it does not appear in equations such as the Schrodinger equation or Klein-Gordon equation seems to be important to the dynamics of a quantum mechanical system in both the time-independent and dependent cases. In the first, $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ "accelerates" only in space, in the latter in both space and time, the second causing a spatial gradient of $E(x,t)$.

Uncertainty Principle

It seems one may obtain some information about the uncertainty principle from the behaviour of $W(x,t)$ under changes in t and x .

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = i \left(\frac{d}{dt} E(x,t) \right) W(x,t) + W(x,t) (-i) E(x,t) \quad \text{and}$$

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) = \left(\frac{d}{dx} \langle p \rangle \right) W(x,t) + i W(x,t) \langle p \rangle \quad \text{((2))}$$

Thus:

$$-\text{Var}(E) = [-\langle E^2 \rangle + \langle E \rangle^2] = \frac{d}{dt} E(x,t) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Var}(p) = [\langle p^2 \rangle - \langle p \rangle^2] = \frac{d}{dx} \langle p \rangle \quad \text{((3))}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} E(x,t) = - \frac{d}{dt} \langle p \rangle \quad \text{from ((1))}$$

If one writes loosely $\frac{d}{dx} E(x,t) = [\Delta E(x,t)] / [\Delta x]$ and the same for other partial derivatives, then ((3)) becomes:

$$\text{Var}(E) [\Delta t] [\Delta t] = \text{Var}(p) [\Delta x] [\Delta x]$$

(It should be noted that one is forcing $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$ to allow for $\Delta E(x,t)$ to be the same in $\frac{d}{dt} E(x,t)$ and $\frac{d}{dx} E(x,t)$. This is a "manipulation", but if it holds one obtains the uncertainty principle with the equality.) This seems to be related to the dynamics of the system as one is linking $\Delta(x)$ and $\Delta(t)$. One might even obtain a "velocity" $\Delta(x)/\Delta(t)$ in such a forced case.

Taking the square root yields a type of uncertainty principle based on variances:

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(E)} \Delta(t) = \sqrt{\text{Var}(p)} \Delta(x) \quad \text{((4))}$$

Here, it should be noted that the conditional average is being used in calculating variances i.e. the probability used to calculate probabilities of functions of p is $f_p(t) \exp(ipx)/W(x,t)$ and that for E is $g(x,E) \exp(-iEt)/W(x,t)$. This is equivalent to taking derivatives in $\frac{d}{dx}$ or $\frac{d}{dt}$ i.e. $\langle p^2 \rangle = -\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t)$.

Linear Relativistic Equations

The Dirac equation is a well-known linear (in $\frac{d}{dt}$ and $\frac{d}{x}$) relativistic equation. In one dimension, however, it has a two component solution instead of $W(x,t)$. It may be shown (2), that if one function is $U(x,t)$, the other is $\frac{d}{dx} U(x,t) / (E-m)$ or $(E+m)$. Thus, one has a function and

another related to its spatial flux to ensure the linear d/dx term in the Dirac equation is really quadratic. Furthermore, even though a linear d/dt exists on the LHS of the Dirac equation, there is an $(i d/dt - m)^{-1}$ or $(i d/dt + m)^{-1}$ on the RHS, so the equation is not strictly linear in d/dt . In (1), an approach is used to obtain a relativistic quantum mechanical equation linear in E . For the bound state solution, the result listed as ((10)) is:

$$E = p^*p / (m+m_0) + 2m U(x,t) / (m+m_0) - U^*U / (m_0+m)c^*c + m_0c^*c$$

This is translated into a quantum mechanical equation by replacing E with $i d/dt W(x,t)$ and p^*p with $-d/dx d/dx W(x,t)$. The m in this equation is the system mass (including rest mass, kinetic energy and potential energy). It seems, however, that $E=mc^*c$ so if E is replaced with $i d/dt W(x,t)$, then $1/(m+m_0)$ may be replaced with $(c^*c i d/dt + m_0)^{-1}$ like in the Dirac case. Thus, the equation is only seemingly linear in E .

In addition, we would like to examine the ideas used in (1) with conditional averages. In (1), the energy of a quantum system is given as $\sqrt{p^*p+m_0^*m_0} + U(x,t)$. Here $c=1$ and $U(x,t)$ a potential. We wish to consider two conditional averages:

$$\langle E \rangle \langle E \rangle = [\langle \sqrt{p^*p+m_0^*m_0} \rangle + U]^2 = U^2 + \langle E \text{ free} \rangle^2 + 2U \langle E \text{ free} \rangle \quad ((5))$$

And

$$\langle E^*E \rangle = \langle [\sqrt{p^*p+m_0^*m_0} + U]^2 \rangle = \langle E^2 \text{ free} \rangle + 2U \langle E \text{ free} \rangle + U^2 \quad ((6))$$

Here E is the full energy including rest mass, kinetic energy and potential energy (according to (1)).

Then:

$$\langle E^*E \rangle - \langle E \rangle \langle E \rangle = \langle E^2 \text{ free} \rangle - \langle E \text{ free} \rangle \langle E \text{ free} \rangle = \langle p^*p \rangle + m_0^*m_0 - \langle E_{\text{free}} \rangle \langle E_{\text{free}} \rangle \quad ((7))$$

$$-d/dt d/dt W(x,t) - \langle E \rangle \langle E \rangle = -d/dx d/dx W(x,t) + m_0^*m_0 - \langle E_{\text{free}} \rangle \langle E_{\text{free}} \rangle \quad ((8))$$

Here $\langle E \text{ free} \rangle = \langle \sqrt{p^*p+m_0^*m_0} \rangle$ and $\langle E \rangle = i d/dt W(x,t)$

It seems, however, that $\langle E \rangle \langle E \rangle$ and $\langle E \text{ free} \rangle \langle E_{\text{free}} \rangle$ are not the same (even though the conditional average of E_{free} uses $f_p(t)$ weights which are influenced by the potential.) Thus, one does not obtain the Klein-Gordon equation using this approach with conditional averages.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems the dynamical equation ((1)), which should hold in both relativistic and non-relativistic cases, follows from the transformation properties of $W(x,t)$ which link $\langle E \rangle$ the conditional average of the full energy to $\langle p \rangle$ the conditional average of the “free” (but constrained) momentum. It should be noted that $\langle p \rangle$ is calculated using the complex probability $f_p(t) \exp(ipx) / W(x,t)$ and so it is linked to an equation (Schrodinger equation, Klein-Gordon etc). Thus, $f_p(t)$ contains information about the energy and potential energy. Nevertheless, for the time dependent case, $d/dt \langle p \rangle \neq 0$ ($d/dt =$ partial derivative) shows that an energy gradient in space is created due to this acceleration in time. $\langle p \rangle$ is already changing in space for the time-independent case (as well as the time-dependent one), so there are two accelerations occurring. $d/dx \langle p \rangle$, however, does not lead to any change in E in x or t in the time-independent case.

References

1. Guangqing Bi, Yuekai Bi Stationary Solutions of the Klein Gordon Equation in a Potential Field <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1008.4224.pdf>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Dirac Equation and Time Flux (preprint, zenodo, 2019)